

Greener Periods, Cleaner Planet: Exploring Women’s Choices of Sustainable Menstrual Products in India

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Abstract—Sanitary napkins play a vital role in promoting women’s health and well-being; however, their life cycle—from raw material extraction and production to consumption and disposal—generates significant waste and poses serious sustainability challenges. To evaluate how these challenges impede the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), this paper applies network analysis and tabular mapping to connect five key dimensions—environment, health, waste management, policy, and awareness—with relevant SDGs and their specific targets. Within this analytical framework, the study systematically evaluates the environmental and health impacts of conventional sanitary pads and highlights the urgent need for sustainable alternatives. Moreover, it investigates how innovative waste management strategies, effective policy mechanisms, and comprehensive educational and awareness initiatives can foster responsible consumption and sustainable disposal practices aligned with the SDGs, thereby promoting a more inclusive, equitable, and environmentally sustainable menstrual hygiene management system.

tampons, menstrual cups, and wipes, sanitary napkins remain the most widely used, owing to their accessibility, affordability, and cultural acceptance [1], [10], [11]. However, adoption patterns remain uneven: while nearly 64% of young women (15–24 years) report using sanitary napkins, only 1.7% use tampons and 0.3% use menstrual cups [2], [9]. The Indian feminine hygiene market, valued at around USD 340 million in 2017 [12], has grown significantly to USD 1.41 billion in 2024 and is projected to reach USD 3.08 billion by 2030, with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 13.91% [13]. This market growth drives the impact of awareness initiatives, improved product accessibility, and broader educational and economic opportunities for women.

1.2. Motivation

Sanitary napkins enable menstruating women to participate fully in daily, educational, and economic life by ensuring comfort, confidence, and hygiene [14], [15]. Typically, these napkins consist of approximately 48% bleached fluff pulp (cellulose-based) for absorbency, 36% plastics such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) for comfort and leak protection, 6% superabsorbent polymer (SAP, usually sodium polyacrylate) for high absorbency, 7% adhesives (mainly synthetic polymers & tackifiers) for bonding of layers, and 3% release paper (plastic coated) for protecting adhesive before use [16]–[18]. Additionally, some contaminants such as dioxin, dioctyltin, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) were found in bleached fluff pulp [19]–[21]. Despite cellulose-based and plant-derived, the high content of plastics and synthetic materials (PE, PP, and SAP) makes most sanitary napkins non-biodegradable [22].

Nearly 36% of India’s total menstruating women use locally or commercially produced sanitary pads [23]–[25], generating vast amounts of waste. A woman typically uses 12–16 pads per cycle, approximately 8,000 to 10,000 pads during her lifetime [16], [26], [27]. Nationally, this results in roughly 12.3 billion pads discarded each year, equivalent to 113,000 tonnes (or 310 tonnes daily) of menstrual waste [28], [29]. Globally, an individual discards 125–150 kg of menstrual products over a lifetime [7], [30], [31]. This alarming waste generation and persistence of non-biodegradable materials, leading to pollution and health risks, constitute the key motivation of this study, emphasizing the need for sustainable and effective waste management solutions.

Fig. 1. Graphical abstract: Pathways to Zero-Waste Menstrual Hygiene

Keywords: *Sanitary Napkin, Environmental Impact, Menstrual Health, Waste Management, Sustainability, Responsible Consumption.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

India, one of the most populous countries in the world, has a large menstruating population. Estimates suggest over 355 million menstruating girls and women in India, representing nearly one-fourth of the total population [1], [2]. The average menstrual cycle begins at menarche around 13 years of age [3], [4] and ends at menopause near 46.5 years [5], [6]. During a reproductive lifespan of 34 to 38 years, women experience approximately 460 cycles, which is more than six years of menstruation [7], [8].

According to NFHS-5 (2019–21) data, 77% of women aged 15–24 years in India exclusively use hygienic menstrual products [2], [9]. Among the available options such as pantyliners,

TABLE I
LINKAGES BETWEEN SDGs, MENSTRUAL HYGIENE TARGETS, AND THE IMPLICATIONS OF CONVENTIONAL SANITARY PAD USAGE

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	Relevant Targets	Conventional Sanitary Pads: Alignment and Misalignment with SDGs and Targets
SDG 1: No Poverty	1.4: Ensure equal rights and access to basic services and resources, especially for the poor and vulnerable	Period poverty limits access to sanitary products; improving affordability and distribution ensures equitable access to menstrual hygiene resources.
SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being	3.7: Universal access to sexual and reproductive health (including menstrual health) 3.9: Reduce illnesses and deaths from hazardous chemicals and pollution	Unsafe sanitary pads expose users to harmful chemicals (e.g., bleaching agents, phthalates); improper disposal contaminates water, affecting health.
SDG 4: Quality Education	4.1: Equal access to education 4.5: Eliminate gender disparities 4.7: Promote education for sustainable development	Lack of menstrual hygiene facilities or awareness leads to school absenteeism; education on sustainable products reduces environmental impacts.
SDG 5: Gender Equality	5.1: End discrimination against women and girls 5.6: Ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health 5.b: Promote enabling technologies to empower women	Limited access to menstrual products undermines gender equity; innovations in product design and disposal enhance empowerment and safety.
SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation	6.2: Access to adequate sanitation and hygiene 6.3: Improve water quality by reducing pollution 6.6: Protect water-related ecosystems 6.b: Strengthen community participation in water and sanitation management	Improper disposal pollutes water bodies; safe disposal and eco-friendly alternatives protect water quality and promote hygiene.
SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth	8.3: Promote productive employment and innovation 8.8: Protect labor rights and ensure safe working conditions	Workers involved in pad production and waste collection face occupational hazards; sustainable enterprises can create safe and green jobs.
SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure	9.1: Develop sustainable infrastructure 9.4: Upgrade industries for resource efficiency and clean technologies	Effective menstrual waste management requires sustainable infrastructure; inadequate systems worsen health risks and social inequities.
SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities	11.6: Reduce environmental impacts of cities	Sanitary pads contribute to urban solid waste; proper management reduces landfill pressure and city pollution.
SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production	12.4: Environmentally sound management of chemicals and waste 12.5: Reduce waste generation 12.8: Promote awareness for sustainable lifestyles	Promotes reusable or biodegradable pads, recycling, and awareness campaigns to minimize waste and chemical contamination.
SDG 13: Climate Action	13.2: Integrate climate change measures into policies	Manufacturing and incineration of pads emit greenhouse gases; reducing plastic and promoting eco-friendly alternatives mitigates climate impact.
SDG 14: Life Below Water	14.1: Reduce marine pollution 14.2: Protect marine ecosystems	Pads discarded into water bodies degrade into microplastics, harming aquatic life; responsible disposal safeguards ecosystems.
SDG 15: Life on Land	15.1: Conserve terrestrial & freshwater ecosystems 15.3: Combat desertification and restore degraded land	Landfilling and burning pads contaminate soil and harm biodiversity; biodegradable products reduce ecological damage.
SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals	17.16: Strengthen global partnerships 17.17: Encourage collaboration among sectors	Cooperation between governments, NGOs, and industries is essential for improving menstrual hygiene management and sustainable disposal systems.

Source: Authors' own compilation.

1.3. Role of Sustainable Development in Menstrual Hygiene

The Brundtland Commission's 1987 report *Our Common Future* defines sustainable development as meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own [32]. It is anchored in three interdependent pillars: environmental, social, and economic, which must remain balanced to achieve true sustainability [33], [34]. In the context of menstrual hygiene, this balance is challenged by the production, use and disposal of sanitary napkins, at times misaligned with multiple *Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)* and their associated targets, as outlined in Table-I.

1.4. Research Gap, Objectives and Contribution of the Study

Despite extensive literature on menstrual hygiene management, few studies integrate its environmental, health, waste management, policy, and educational dimensions within a unified sustainability framework. Existing research often treats these aspects separately, resulting in a limited understanding of how conventional sanitary napkin practices collectively relate to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their

specific targets. Adopting an *integrative research approach*, this study aims to bridge that gap by:

- (i) To analyze the *environmental implications* associated with the production, usage, and disposal of sanitary napkins.
- (ii) To explain the effects of sanitary napkin use on *physical and reproductive health*, with particular attention to hygiene, safety, and gender equity in access to menstrual products.
- (iii) To review and critically evaluate current *waste management* practices for sanitary napkin disposal and assess their relative effectiveness.
- (iv) To discuss the role of *policy and governance* frameworks in regulating, managing, and promoting sustainable menstrual hygiene practices.
- (v) To explore the extent of *awareness* and the impact of *educational initiatives* related to menstrual health and the adoption of sustainable menstrual products.

The contribution of the paper lies in its *dual analytical framework* that links sanitary napkin production, usage, and

disposal to the SDGs across the five dimensions. It combines *network analysis* (Figure 2) to visualize interconnections among SDGs with *tabular mapping* (Tables IV, V & VI) to align specific targets within each dimension. This integrated method provides a structured and systematic understanding of how menstrual hygiene practices intersect with and promote sustainability objectives.

Fig. 2. Interconnectivity of Sanitary Napkin Dimensions with SDGs

1.5. Structure of the Paper

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Sections 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 examine five critical dimensions of sanitary napkins—Environment, Health, Waste Management, Policy and Governance, and Awareness and Education, respectively. Section 7 synthesizes the findings, highlights implications, and includes the authors’ reflections. Finally, Section 8 presents the concluding remarks.

2. ENVIRONMENT

The life cycle of sanitary napkins from raw material extraction to manufacturing, use, and disposal imposes significant environmental burdens [18], [35], [36]. These burdens include chemical pollution, plastic accumulation, landfill saturation, water contamination, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Collectively, these impacts conflict with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), notably **SDG 6** (Clean Water and Sanitation), **SDG 12** (Responsible Consumption and Production), **SDG 13** (Climate Action), **SDG 14** (Life Below Water), and **SDG 15** (Life on Land).

2.1. Chemical Pollution

The production and use of sanitary napkins release hazardous chemicals that pose risks to both environmental and human health, thereby undermining the objectives of *SDG 12*.

During the stage of *raw material extraction*, chemicals such as volatile organic compounds (VOCs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), pesticides, and chlorine used in pulp bleaching are released into the environment [26], [27], [36], [37].

The *manufacturing phase* of sanitary napkins involves numerous toxic substances, including dioxins, organochlorines, antibacterial agents (e.g., triclosan, silver nanoparticles), and heavy metals such as cadmium, lead, and mercury [38]. Residual chemicals such as di-isobutyl phthalate (DiBP), bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), and di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP) have also been detected in sanitary napkins, raising

concerns about exposure in women [37], [39], [40]. Superabsorbent polymers (SAPs), synthesized from hydrophilic polymers such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), acrylamide, polyethylene oxide (PEO), and sodium polyacrylate, can absorb fluids several hundred times their weight [18], [41]. Moreover, additives such as synthetic fragrances, musk compounds, pigments, fungicides, bleaches, and stabilizers are commonly used to enhance product performance, further increasing the overall chemical load [18], [27].

In the *use phase*, users are directly exposed to phthalates, VOCs, fragrances, and antibacterial agents [38].

Finally, in the *disposal and end-of-life* stage, common practices such as incineration and landfilling result in the release of dioxins, furans, PAHs, carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NOx), particulate matter, heavy metals, microplastics, low-density polyethylene (LDPE) leachates, and other persistent organic pollutants (POPs) [36], [42], [43]. These emissions not only contaminate air, soil, and water but also contribute to long-term ecological damage and human health risks.

2.2. Plastic Pollution

Plastic pollution from menstrual waste hampers progress toward *SDG 6* and *SDG 12*. Disposable sanitary napkins, composed of nearly 90% non-biodegradable plastics and synthetics [26], [43], [44], are major contributors to plastic waste. The top “fabric” layer is made of a thin woven plastic sheet, while polyethylene wings, adhesive strips, and superabsorbent polymer (SAP) gels incorporated during *manufacturing* further increase the plastic burden [45]. Including packaging, each pad contributes the equivalent of about four plastic bags, or approximately 2 grams of non-biodegradable plastic [12], which gradually degrades into microplastics, accumulating in soil and water ecosystems over time.

2.3. Landfill Accumulation

The disposal of non-biodegradable sanitary napkins undermines *SDG 12*, and *SDG 15* by driving unsustainable waste practices and contributing to landfill accumulation. As single-use napkins are not categorized as biomedical waste, they are often mixed with household garbage, buried in open areas, or dumped into water bodies [26]. With an estimated decomposition period of 500–800 years, their prolonged persistence leads to soil degradation, water contamination, and serious threats to marine ecosystems and human health [7], [11], [15], [46], [47].

2.4. Water Pollution

Improper disposal of sanitary napkins threatens *SDG 6* and *SDG 14*, as pads and tampons often enter freshwater and marine ecosystems instead of solid waste streams [26]. In India, over one billion non-compostable pads are discarded monthly through sewage and landfills [12]. Containing polyethylene backsheets, polypropylene covers, and SAP cores, these products break down into micro- and nanoplastics that persist for decades [18]. These particles are ingested by aquatic organisms such as plankton, fish, turtles, and seabirds, leading to internal injuries, starvation, and broader ecological damage [12], [47].

2.5. Greenhouse Gas Emissions

Greenhouse gas emissions from the production and disposal of sanitary napkins violate *SDG 13*, which focuses on emission reduction. Over a woman's reproductive lifetime, the use of up to 10,000 pads [12], [48] contributes significantly to resource depletion and greenhouse gas release during degradation. Globally, the annual production and use of about 12 billion disposable menstrual products generate an estimated 245,000 tonnes of CO₂ [26]. The carbon footprint of disposable sanitary napkins is approximately 5.3 kg CO₂ per user each year (equivalent to emissions from around 49,020 automobiles), whereas menstrual cups produce less than 0.1 kg CO₂ annually [46], [49]–[51]. Additionally, energy-intensive plastic manufacturing and disposal through incineration or open burning release CO₂, methane, and other pollutants, further aggravating climate change [52].

3. HEALTH

Menstrual hygiene products are essential to women's health, dignity, and human rights [53], [54]. However, conventional sanitary napkins, while providing short-term comfort, pose significant long-term health challenges [36]. Their unsafe chemical composition and improper disposal practices endanger both users and waste handlers, thereby conflicting with several Sustainable Development Goals—**SDG 3** (Good Health and Well-being), **SDG 5** (Gender Equality), **SDG 6** (Clean Water and Sanitation), **SDG 8** (Decent Work and Economic Growth), and **SDG 12** (Responsible Consumption and Production) by compromising health, safety, and sustainability.

3.1. Toxic Chemicals in Sanitary Napkins and Associated Health Risks

Commercial sanitary napkins may contain chemical residues such as dioxins (from chlorine bleaching of wood pulp or cotton), pesticide residues (from conventionally grown cotton), synthetic fragrances, and phthalates. Although present at low levels, these substances have been associated with potential long-term health concerns [40], [55], [56]. Since these products are in direct contact with the sensitive vaginal and vulvar skin, the chemicals can be readily absorbed into the body, increasing systemic exposure [38]. Such exposure has been linked to endocrine disruption, allergic reactions, reproductive disorders, and impaired immunity [27], [57]. Moreover, scented sanitary napkins containing about 5 mg of perfume per pad, often include allergens such as cinnamaldehyde and cinnamic alcohol [58]. Studies have also identified five allergenic fragrance components: limonene, linalool, citronellal, geraniol, and hydroxycitronellal in sanitary napkins [18], [59].

Among the most concerning contaminants in sanitary pads are phthalates, particularly DiBP, DEHP, and DnBP found at significant levels [37]. These compounds, introduced during manufacturing or leaching from plastic and paper-based components, can be absorbed through vaginal and vulvar tissues, posing serious health risks [38], [39]. In addition, disposable pads often contain parabens (used as antimicrobial agents) and triclocarbons (as antibacterial agents), heightening concerns about chronic exposure [60]. Recent studies reveal that sanitary pads sold in India contain higher levels of harmful chemicals than those in the USA, Europe, and Japan.

Tests on major Indian sanitary pad brands detected chlorine, dioxins, furans, volatile organic compounds (acetone, isopropyl alcohol, and toluene), and high levels of phthalates (DBP and DEHP), indicating potential long-term health risks [36].

3.2. Specific Health Outcomes

a. Dermatological effects: Women frequently report skin irritation, itching, rashes, and recurrent infections associated with the use of low-quality or chemically treated menstrual products [57], [61].

b. Reproductive and urinary tract infections (RTIs & UTIs): The warm, moist environment of sanitary pads, combined with chemical additives, may increase susceptibility to reproductive tract infections (RTIs) and urinary tract infections (UTIs), particularly when pads are worn for extended durations [18], [19], [21], [62], [63].

c. Heavy metal exposure and systemic toxicity: Menstrual pads often contain heavy metals such as cadmium, lead, and mercury, in addition to bleaching agents. These substances can accumulate in the body, elevating the risk of kidney disease, cardiovascular complications, and systemic inflammatory conditions [26], [27], [64].

d. Reproductive health concerns: Adverse impacts on vaginal and vulvar health, alteration of vaginal microflora, and possible links to reproductive disorders such as endometriosis have also been noted. Organic solvents and additives used in sanitary pads may further increase risks during pregnancy and contribute to fertility issues [64].

e. Neurological and autoimmune implications: Certain organic solvents and chemical residues in sanitary pads are also associated with autoimmune disorders and impaired neurological development including paralysis and memory loss, highlighting the broader systemic risks of prolonged exposure [44], [64].

3.3. Health Hazards Among Sanitation Workers and Waste Pickers

a. Direct exposure to contaminated waste: Sanitation workers and informal waste pickers face serious occupational hazards from discarded sanitary napkins contaminated with menstrual blood and pathogens such as HIV, HBV, HCV, and bacteria [65], [66]. In India, menstrual waste is rarely segregated and is usually mixed with municipal solid waste, exposing workers to unprotected contact during collection, sorting, and transport [67]. The absence of personal protective equipment (PPE) and limited occupational health training further increase risks, leading to higher incidences of skin infections, respiratory diseases, gastroenteritis, and viral hepatitis among waste handlers [65].

b. Health issues among waste pickers: Around four million women rag pickers in India are exposed to menstrual waste daily, facing multiple health risks [68]. Common problems include skin infections, respiratory illnesses from burning pads, injuries, and blood-borne infections due to lack of protective equipment (such as gloves, masks, and boots) and medical check-ups, along with psychological distress from stigma and discrimination [12], [69]–[71].

4. WASTE MANAGEMENT

The increasing use of disposable sanitary napkins has resulted in a sharp rise in menstrual waste, much of which is

handled through unsafe and unsustainable methods [42], [72], [73]. In India, this waste is usually mixed with household garbage without segregation. Rural disposal practices include burial, open burning, or dumping in pits [15], while in urban areas, pads are often flushed, discarded in bins, or sent through municipal waste systems [74]. These methods pose serious environmental and health hazards. Effective solutions require integrated, sustainable waste management strategies aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) particularly **SDG 3** (Good Health and Well-being), **SDG 6** (Clean Water and Sanitation), **SDG 8** (Decent Work and Economic Growth), **SDG 9** (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), **SDG 12** (Responsible Consumption and Production), and **SDG 13** (Climate Action).

4.1. Innovative Waste Management Strategies

a. Aakar Innovations: Aakar, a hybrid social enterprise, empowers women to produce and distribute affordable, high-quality sanitary napkins as well as promoting menstrual hygiene awareness. Its *Anandi pad*, India's first Government of India lab-certified (ISO-17088) nearly 100% compostable and biodegradable sanitary pad, offers a sustainable alternative for both rural and urban users [44], [75]. Other notable initiatives include *Mukti Pads* (by the Society for Rural Industrialisation), *Ssodashi* (by Jindal Power and Steel Plant), and *Freedays* (by the Government of India) [76].

b. Rural Disposal Innovations: Several low-cost, eco-friendly innovations are improving rural menstrual waste disposal. The Vatsalya Foundation's clay and cement incinerators, *Ashudhinashak*, can burn multiple sanitary napkins simultaneously without smoke, ensuring safer disposal [15], [77]. Likewise, *latrines with shoulder-level chutes* use chemical agents to speed up decomposition, offering hygienic solutions in areas without formal waste systems [15]. Moreover, *color-coded disposal bags* provided by manufacturers help promote proper segregation and disposal [15], [78].

c. Dahini: The low-cost sanitary napkin incinerator *Dahini*, priced around Rs 4000, provides an affordable and eco-friendly solution for menstrual waste disposal. It ensures safe and hygienic management of used pads and can be installed in public washrooms, hostels, schools, colleges, and homes, helping reduce landfill waste, odours, and infection risks [11].

4.2. Advanced Waste Management Strategies

Technologies such as pyrolysis, gasification, and resource recovery can effectively address the increasing burden of sanitary waste [46].

a. Pyrolysis: Pyrolysis sustainably manages sanitary napkin waste by thermally decomposing materials in the absence of oxygen, minimizing landfill load and pollution. It recovers valuable products such as *pyro-oil* and *pyro-char*, which can be used for energy generation, carbon black production, and chemical synthesis, promoting a circular and resource-efficient waste management system [46], [49].

b. Co-gasification: Co-gasification enables resource recovery from used sanitary napkin waste by converting its plastic and biomass components into *producer gas* (type of fuel gas) when blended with biomass (like sawdust) in a gasifier. This process produces high-temperature gas that can be used for *thermal applications*, while also reducing waste volume and clinker formation. It transforms sanitary napkin

waste into a valuable energy resource, promoting sustainable waste-to-energy conversion [49], [79], [80]

4.3. Circular Economy Models

The circular economy aims to minimize waste and maximize resource efficiency by promoting a *closed-loop system* where materials are reused, repaired, recycled, or regenerated. Unlike the traditional linear model of *take-make-use-dispose* (figure 3), it emphasizes *sustainable resource circulation* (figure 4) [81], [82]. The following approaches demonstrate its application in menstrual hygiene management.

Fig. 3. Linear Economy

Fig. 4. Circular Economy

4.3.1. Community-Based Approaches: Community initiatives significantly support circular economy goals of reuse and recycling. For instance, Pune's Red Dot Campaign [83], [84] and PadCare Labs' recycling model [85], which promote responsible waste collection and material recovery. In rural Uttar Pradesh, earthen "*matka*"-based eco-incinerators provide an affordable and safe method for sanitary waste disposal in the absence of formal systems, helping to eliminate unsafe open burning [86].

4.3.2. Reusable Sanitary Products: Economic sustainability is a critical dimension of menstrual hygiene management, as disposable sanitary napkins impose a recurring financial burden, particularly on women in low-income households [87], [88]. In the long run, the cumulative cost of disposables far outweighs that of reusable alternatives such as *cloth pads*, *menstrual cups*, and *period panties* (see Table II), which offer longer lifespans and substantially reduce waste generation [89]–[91]. Among these, menstrual cups stand out for their durability, minimal waste, and strong environmental advantages [51], [92]–[94].

4.3.3. Sustainable Product Alternatives: Beyond reusable options, eco-friendly menstrual products are emerging as sustainable alternatives to conventional disposables, focusing on biodegradability and reduced waste generation [95] (see Table III).

4.3.3a. Agricultural Waste-Based Pads: Bamboo fiber pads, made from 100% cellulose, are biodegradable, antibacterial, and highly absorbent, offering better performance than cotton [96], [97]. Banana fiber pads, sold under brands like *Saathi* and *Sanfe*, are low-cost, compostable within a year, and provide high tensile strength and absorbency [15], [98]–[101]. The *Sakhi* pad, made from pinewood pulp with

TABLE II
REUSABLE ECO-FRIENDLY MENSTRUAL PRODUCTS – USABILITY, IMPACT & SAVINGS

Product Type	Main Material(s)	Usability (Years)	Biodegradation Time	Environmental Benefits	Disposables Replaced (if a woman uses 12-14 napkins / cycle)
Menstrual Cups	Medical-grade silicone, rubber, or Thermoplastic Elastomer (TPE)	5–10	Although not biodegradable, very low waste	Most durable, minimal waste, cost-effective	800-1600
Cloth Pads (Reusable)	Cotton / organic cotton	4–5	6–12 months (if composted)	Washable, affordable, reduces cumulative waste	650-850
Period Panties	Cotton + synthetic absorbent textiles	2–5	Mixed (synthetic parts persist)	Washable, convenient, reduces waste	350-850

Source: Authors' compilation based on literature [94], [106], [118]–[121]

silicon paper, butter paper, non-woven fabric, and cotton, decomposes within eight days in soil [102]. Likewise, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH)-treated pineapple leaf fiber (PALF) pulp shows superior water absorption [103], while corn husk fibers blended with wood pulp (30–50%) yield affordable, hygienic pads comparable to branded disposables [104].

4.3.3b. Invasive Plant Waste–Based Pads: Papyrus and waste paper–based napkins such as *Makapads* offer biodegradable, low-cost solutions suitable for low-income communities [47], [105], [106]. Similarly, water hyacinth, an invasive weed, has been utilized to produce absorbent pads marketed as *Jani* [99], [107], [108].

4.3.3c. Textile Waste–Based Pads: Pads made from cotton fluff waste combined with natural antibacterial agents such as neem and orange peel, along with Polylactic Acid (PLA) films, are fully biodegradable [109]. Other innovations include pads from jute industry waste and organic cotton napkins that are compostable, breathable, and skin-friendly, often blended with jute or hemp for improved leak resistance [7], [110], [111].

4.3.3d. Locally Available Waste Materials: Replacing costly wood pulp with agro-residues such as bagasse or cleaned textile waste (e.g., cotton knitwear) enables low-cost sanitary pad production [112]–[114]. These community-based models also generate employment for women's groups while promoting affordability and eco-friendliness [115].

4.3.3e. Hemp Sanitary Pads: Pads made from *Cannabis sativa* fibers are breathable, durable, and highly absorbent [116], [117]. As hemp needs less water and fewer pesticides than cotton, it offers a promising sustainable alternative. Similarly, Hempur pads, made from unbleached bamboo pulp, are plant-based, biodegradable, hypoallergenic, and ultra-soft [22].

4.3.4. Life-Cycle Analysis: By assessing environmental impacts from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal, Life-Cycle Analysis (LCA) serves as a critical evaluation tool to compare the environmental performance of menstrual hygiene products [51]. It also helps guide circular economy strategies, ensuring that reusable and biodegradable options genuinely advance sustainability [50], [123], [124].

5. POLICY AND GOVERNANCE

Both government and non-government organizations should actively promote awareness of proper menstrual waste management. The government can allocate dedicated funds to municipal bodies and NGOs for establishing and maintaining women-friendly sanitation facilities. Such initiatives support multiple SDGs—**SDG 3** (Good Health and Well-being), **SDG**

5 (Gender Equality), **SDG 6** (Clean Water and Sanitation), **SDG 8** (Decent Work and Economic Growth), **SDG 9** (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), **SDG 11** (Sustainable Cities and Communities), **SDG 12** (Responsible Consumption and Production), and **SDG 17** (Partnerships for the Goals) by improving health, empowering women, creating employment, and promoting sustainable infrastructure through multi-stakeholder collaboration.

5.1. Policy Framework.

a. Bio-Medical Waste Management Rule, 1998: This rule primarily addressed waste generated from healthcare institutions such as hospitals, nursing homes, and clinics. Under its provisions, sanitary pads used in medical settings, particularly in maternity wards, were categorized as bio-medical waste and required proper disposal through incineration or other scientific treatment methods. However, it excluded household menstrual waste, creating a major governance gap [125].

b. The Swachh Bharat (Swachh Vidyalaya campaign, 2014): It was launched to ensure that every school in India has functional and well-maintained Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) facilities, including soap, private spaces for changing, adequate water for washing, and proper disposal facilities for used menstrual absorbents [126], [127].

c. The Solid Waste Management Rules, 2016: These rules define sanitary waste to include used diapers, sanitary pads, tampons, and condoms. They impose clear responsibilities: citizens are required to wrap pads securely in pouches and hand them over separately to waste collectors, while municipalities are tasked with ensuring proper collection, transportation, and scientific disposal [128], [129].

5.2. Government Scheme on Subsidized Sanitary Napkins

The Government of India has improved menstrual hygiene access through initiatives like the *Menstrual Hygiene Scheme* (MHS, 2011) under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), which provides low-cost sanitary pads through ASHA workers, schools, and health centers [130]. On March 8, 2018, it introduced the *Suvidha 100% oxy-biodegradable* sanitary napkins, available at Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) stores, initially priced at ₹10 for four pads and later reduced to ₹1 per pad, now distributed through over 8,000 Kendras nationwide [126], [131]–[134]. This initiative promotes Swachhta (cleanliness), Swasthya (health), and Suvidha (convenience), ensuring affordable and quality menstrual healthcare for economically disadvantaged women [135].

TABLE III
SINGLE-USE ECO-FRIENDLY MENSTRUAL PRODUCTS – MATERIALS, IMPACT & BIODEGRADATION

Product Type	Main Material(s)	Biodegradable Time	Environmental Benefits
Bamboo Fiber Pads	100% cellulose bamboo fiber	0.5–1 year	Biodegradable, less pesticide
Banana Fiber Pads (Saathi, Sanfe)	Banana fiber	0.5–1 year	Agro-waste utilization, compostable
Pineapple Leaf Fiber (PALF) Pads	PALF pulp	<1 year	Superior absorption, biodegradable
Pinewood Pulp Pads (Sakhi)	Pinewood cellulose pulp + non-woven cover	<1 year	biodegradable; supports rural women-led manufacturing
Corn Husk Fiber Pads	Corn husk + wood pulp	<1 year	Reduces virgin pulp demand
Papyrus / Makapads	Papyrus + waste paper	<1 year	Low-cost, biodegradable, community-based
Water Hyacinth Pads (Jani)	Invasive water hyacinth	<1 year	Converts invasive weed into usable product
Textile Waste Pads	Cotton fluff waste + PLA	0.5–1 year	Waste valorization, compostable
Jute / Organic Cotton Pads	Jute waste + organic cotton	<1 year	Eco-friendly, compostable
Bagasse / Agro-Residue Pads	Bagasse + textile waste	<1 year	Low-cost, women-led production
Hemp Pads (Hempur)	Hemp + bamboo pulp	<1 year	Less water & pesticide use vs cotton

Source: Authors' compilation based on literature [96]–[104], [122]

5.3. Policy towards Job Opportunity and Sanitation

Another noteworthy initiative involves promoting the local production and distribution of biodegradable sanitary napkins, constituting a synergistic policy approach. This strategy simultaneously fosters women's entrepreneurship and employment through self-help groups [136], enhances menstrual hygiene management, mitigates environmental degradation, and contributes to sustainable rural development [137]–[139].

5.4. Government tools

Several governance tools have emerged to reinforce sustainable menstrual waste management. *Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)* frameworks ensure that manufacturers remain accountable for the entire lifecycle of their products, from design to disposal [129], [139], [140]. *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)* commitments from sanitary product manufacturers can further promote biodegradable or reusable alternatives, support recycling initiatives, fund awareness campaigns and addressing stigma [141].

5.5. Infrastructure, Regulations, and Technology

Effective menstrual waste management requires integrated infrastructure, supportive regulations, and context-appropriate technologies. Persistent gaps in rural areas across India, Bangladesh, and Nepal reveal how inadequate infrastructure restricts safe menstrual practices and reinforces social inequities [142]–[144]. In higher education institutions, limited sanitary facilities, lack of safe disposal mechanisms, and inadequate water supply continue to hinder hygienic and dignified menstrual management [145]–[147]. Strengthening infrastructure and adopting sustainable management practices are thus crucial to protect health and minimize environmental impacts.

5.6. Global Best Practices

Global initiatives emphasize menstrual health as a key component of gender-responsive *Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH)* services. SDG 6.2 explicitly recognizes menstrual needs, calling for universal and equitable access to sanitation and hygiene by 2030 [148]. Complementing this, the *World Health Assembly resolution of 2023* urges immediate action to curb plastic pollution from the production, use, and disposal

of disposable menstrual products, highlighting the interconnected risks to human, animal, and environmental health [26].

6. AWARENESS AND EDUCATION

Awareness and education form the cornerstone of sustainable menstrual hygiene management. Integrating the distribution of sanitary napkins among the girls of low-income groups, menstrual health and sustainability into school curricula ensures that both girls and boys receive accurate information, helping to challenge stigma, normalize open discussion, and promote healthy practices [14], [149]–[151]. These initiatives directly contribute to **SDG 1** (No Poverty, **particularly target 1.4**: ensuring equal rights and access to basic services and resources), **SDG 4** (Quality Education), **SDG 5** (Gender Equality), and **SDG 6** (Clean Water and Sanitation).

6.1. Period Poverty and Accessibility

Poverty exacerbates menstrual health challenges by limiting access to safe and affordable products [48], [152], [153] that conflicts **SDG 1 (target 1.4)**. Many women and girls, particularly in rural areas, are forced to rely on non-hygienic alternatives, such as old cloth or ash, due to financial constraints. According to *World Bank estimates*, nearly 500 million women and girls worldwide experience period poverty, driven largely by socio-economic inequalities [26], [154]–[156]. Addressing period poverty requires not only improving affordability and accessibility but also incorporating menstrual health into broader poverty alleviation strategies.

6.2. Menstrual Stigma and Gender Inequality

Limited access to safe and sustainable menstrual products perpetuates entrenched gender inequalities, directly hindering progress towards **SDG 5**. Menstruation related stigma, negative attitudes, mobility restrictions, absenteeism, dropout from school or work, and the lack of menstrual-friendly infrastructure reinforce discriminatory practices that marginalize women and girls [48], [157]–[163]. These barriers not only restrict educational and economic participation but also institutionalize gender-based exclusion [156], [164], [165].

6.3. Awareness for Sustainable Choices

Awareness must extend to the environmental implications of menstrual products. Conventional napkins, largely composed of plastic, create persistent waste management challenges. Promoting biodegradable alternatives can encourage a shift toward sustainable menstrual hygiene practices [89], [95], [101], [166]. Integrating menstrual health education [167] with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) further emphasizes the crucial role of teachers and mothers in reducing school drop-outs among rural girls through improved menstrual hygiene management [130], [168]. Collectively, these initiatives not only enable women to manage menstruation with dignity but also advance ecological sustainability and broader social well-being [169], [170].

7. DISCUSSION

7.1. Summary of Findings

Menstrual challenges across five dimensions—environment, health, waste management, policy & governance, and awareness & education—intersect with multiple Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets, highlighting both critical areas of concern and opportunities for positive impact.

a. Environmental Issues and Sustainability Challenges: Sanitary napkins substantially contribute to environmental degradation, violating multiple Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets (see Table IV). The non-biodegradable plastics and toxic chemicals used in their production lead to soil and water contamination, undermining SDGs 6.3, 6.4, and 12.4. Their accumulation in landfills reduces land productivity and disrupts terrestrial ecosystems, contravening SDGs 12.5 and 15.1. Moreover, open burning of menstrual waste releases greenhouse gases and toxic emissions, exacerbating climate change impacts and hindering progress toward SDGs 13.1 and 13.2. The leaching of chemicals and microplastics into waterways further endangers aquatic biodiversity and hampers conservation efforts, violating SDGs 6.6, 14.1, and 14.2.

b. Health Risks and Sustainability Challenges: From a health perspective (see Table IV), prolonged exposure to chemicals such as dioxins and synthetic fragrances in sanitary napkins poses systemic health risks, violating SDG 12.4 on safe chemical management. Direct contact may cause reproductive and urinary infections, contravening SDG 5.6, while inadequate disposal and sanitation heighten hygiene-related diseases, challenging SDG 6.2. Informal waste handlers also face occupational hazards from unsafe waste handling, violating SDG 8.8. Collectively, these health and safety risks conflict with SDG 3.9, which targets reduced illness from hazardous substances, highlighting the need for safer and more sustainable menstrual hygiene practices.

c. Sustainable Waste Management Strategies: Effective waste management strategies for sanitary napkins contribute to the achievement of multiple SDG targets (see Table V). The adoption of biodegradable and compostable pads reduces hazardous exposure and waste generation, aligning with SDG 3.9, 12.4, and 12.5. Community-based and women-led initiatives promote inclusive participation and create green livelihood opportunities, supporting SDG 6.b and 8.3. Furthermore, eco-friendly disposal systems and advanced waste processing technologies enhance sanitation, recycling, and climate resilience, thereby advancing SDG 12.4, 12.5, and 13.2. Circular economy approaches and reusable menstrual

products, supported by life-cycle assessments, improve resource efficiency and encourage sustainable production systems consistent with SDG 6.2, 8.3, and 9.4.

d. Policy and Governance: Despite several policy initiatives, significant gaps persist in achieving holistic sustainability in menstrual hygiene management (see Table VI). The Bio-Medical Waste Management Rules (1998) exclude household menstrual waste, resulting in health risks, water contamination, and improper disposal, violating SDG 3.9, 6.3, 11.6, and 12.4. Similarly, subsidized sanitary napkin schemes, though improving access and reproductive health, often lack adequate disposal systems, indirectly conflicting with SDG 12.4. Persistent challenges in infrastructure, technology, and governance further hinder progress toward SDG 5.b, 6.2, 9.1, and 11.6.

Conversely, national initiatives such as the Swachh Bharat: Swachh Vidyalaya Campaign (2014) and the Solid Waste Management Rules (2016) have strengthened sanitation and hygiene systems, aligning with SDG 11.6, 12.4, and 12.5. Government programs like the Menstrual Hygiene Scheme and Suidha have further advanced reproductive health and gender equity, supporting SDG 3.7, 5.6, and 6.b. In addition, policy mechanisms such as Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), and employment-linked sanitation initiatives foster sustainable production, waste reduction, and decent work opportunities, contributing to SDG 8.3, 12.5, and 17.17. At the global level, cooperation on sustainable menstrual products promotes shared knowledge, innovation, and capacity building, thereby advancing SDG 17.16.

e. Education and Awareness: Social and systemic barriers continue to impede effective menstrual hygiene management (see Table VI). Period poverty, limited product access, and cultural stigma disproportionately affect marginalized groups, violating SDG 1.4, 4.5, 5.1, and 6.2. Conversely, integrating menstrual health education and promoting sustainable choices empower women and communities, advancing gender equality, environmental awareness, and inclusive participation in hygiene initiatives that aligning SDG 4.7, 5.6, 6.b.

TABLE IV
ENVIRONMENTAL AND HEALTH IMPACTS OF SANITARY NAPKINS WITH
SDG TARGETS VIOLATED

Aspect / Issue	SDG Targets Violated
A. Environmental Impacts	
Chemical pollution	6.3, 12.4
Plastic pollution	6.3, 6.4, 12.4
Landfill accumulation	12.5, 15.1
Water pollution	6.3, 6.6, 14.1, 14.2
GHG emissions	13.1, 13.2
B. Health Risks	
Chemical and systemic exposure	3.9, 12.4
Reproductive and skin issues	3.9, 5.6
Infectious and hygiene-related risks	3.9, 6.2
Occupational hazards for waste workers	3.9, 6.2, 8.8, 12.4

Source: Compiled by the authors

7.2. Reflections and Insights from the Authors

As women researchers, our engagement with this issue emerges from both academic and personal inquiry. Despite its significant environmental impact, menstrual waste management remains under-researched in India. Drawing on peer observations, professional networks, lived experiences, and

TABLE V
WASTE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR SANITARY NAPKINS WITH SDG TARGETS ALIGNED

Aspect / Issue	SDG Targets Aligned
C. Waste Management Strategies	
Biodegradable / compostable pads	3.9, 12.4, 12.5
Community / women-led initiatives	6.b, 8.3, 12.4
Eco-friendly rural disposal	12.4, 12.5, 13.2
Advanced waste technologies	12.4, 12.5, 13.2
Circular economy models	12.4, 12.5, 13.2, 8.3
Reusable menstrual products	3.9, 6.2, 12.5
Sustainable alternatives (agricultural, textile, hemp, plant-based)	12.4, 12.5, 13.2
Life-cycle analysis	12.4, 12.5, 9.4

Source: Compiled by the authors

TABLE VI
POLICY, GOVERNANCE, AND SOCIAL DIMENSIONS OF SANITARY NAPKINS WITH SDG TARGETS

Aspect / Issue	SDG Targets Violated	SDG Aligned Targets
D. Policy and Governance		
Bio-Medical Waste Rule, 1998	3.9, 6.3, 11.6, 12.4 (Household waste exclusion)	–
Swachh Vidyalaya Campaign, 2014	–	5.6, 6.2, 6.b
Solid Waste Rules, 2016	–	6.3, 11.6, 12.4, 12.5
Subsidized Napkin Schemes (MHS, Suvidha)	12.4 (though pads are supplied, improper disposal risks)	3.7, 5.6, 6.b, 12.5
Job and Sanitation Policies	–	8.3
EPR and CSR tools	–	12.4, 12.5, 17.17
Infrastructure, regulations, & technology	5.b, 6.2, 9.1, 11.6	–
Global practices	–	17.16
E. Education and Awareness		
Period poverty and access	1.4, 5.1, 6.2	–
Menstrual stigma and discrimination	5.1, 4.5	–
Awareness integration and sustainable choices	–	4.7, 5.6, 6.b

Source: Compiled by the authors

existing studies, we identify key interrelated challenges and insights outlined below.

a. Environmental and Policy Context: Despite existing waste management policies in India, implementation remains weak. Used sanitary pads are commonly discarded with household waste in landfills or open dumps. Their plastic and polymer components decompose extremely slowly, leading to long-term environmental pollution and posing health risks to unprotected waste handlers.

b. Socio-Cultural Barriers and Misconceptions: Observations from peer groups, neighbourhoods and professional networks reveal persistent socio-cultural and psychological barriers to adopting sustainable menstrual products. Misconceptions about menstrual cups, especially concerns over insertion, comfort, and sterilization remain common, largely due to limited menstrual education and deep-rooted cultural taboos.

c. Economic Constraints and Market Accessibility: The adoption of biodegradable sanitary napkins remains limited due to low awareness and affordability issues. Many women

lack access to retail sources, and the higher cost such as Anandi pads priced around ₹16.57 each versus ₹6.50 for regular brands, deters consumers, particularly those from lower-income groups.

d. Government Initiatives and Implementation Challenges: The Government of India's *Suvidha* scheme, offering 100% oxy-biodegradable pads at ₹1 each through around 8,000 centres, is a promising step toward menstrual sustainability. However, limited public awareness and uneven distribution have curtailed its potential. Broader outreach and expansion of distribution networks could facilitate behavioural change toward sustainable menstrual practices.

e. Post-Use Disposal and Public Awareness: Even biodegradable products are often discarded improperly, wrapped in plastic and mixed with general waste, preventing effective decomposition. Without effective education and infrastructure, the environmental benefits of biodegradable alternatives cannot be fully realized.

f. Toward Sustainable and Equitable Menstrual Practices: Creating sustainable menstrual practices requires more than individual change—it demands systemic support, policy commitment, and institutional advocacy. Empowering women with knowledge and affordable eco-friendly choices can make menstrual hygiene both environmentally responsible and socially equitable.

Moreover, our observations highlight that menstrual sustainability is not only an environmental necessity but also a matter of social justice. With greater awareness, accessibility, and policy coordination, small individual actions can collectively drive significant environmental and social transformation.

8. CONCLUSION

Conventional sanitary pads contribute substantially to environmental degradation through plastic and chemical pollution, energy-intensive manufacturing, and greenhouse gas emissions, while also posing significant health risks to users and waste handlers. To address these interlinked challenges, this study employs a dual analytical framework integrating network analysis and tabular mapping to explore the interconnections between sanitary napkin production, use, and disposal practices across five dimensions—environmental, health, waste management, policy, and awareness, and their interactions with relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and corresponding targets.

A holistic and multidimensional strategy that combines technological innovation, policy reform, and educational initiatives together with the promotion of biodegradable and compostable alternatives, circular economy approaches, and eco-friendly disposal practices can substantially reduce environmental impacts and health risks. Policies ensuring safe disposal, equitable access, sustainable production, innovative waste management, and women's empowerment, supported by comprehensive awareness programs, are vital to encourage informed, inclusive, and sustainable menstrual hygiene practices.

By bridging academic analysis with practical insights, this study offers actionable guidance for educators, policymakers, NGOs, and industry stakeholders to facilitate behavioral change and advance both environmental and social well-being. Although the focus is on India, the proposed framework and findings hold broader relevance for other developing contexts, contributing to global policy discourse on sustainability

and gender equity. Ultimately, the study highlights the urgent need for coordinated efforts across education, policy, and community engagement to foster environmentally responsible and socially just menstrual hygiene management.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Durairaj, P. Aparnavi, S. Narayanan, S. Mahantshetti, S. Dhandapani, J. Shanmugam, R. Rathinamoorthy, and M. Kumar, "Utilization of modern menstrual methods and related unmet needs among college going women in coimbatore district: a descriptive cross-sectional study," *BMC Women's Health*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 78, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-024-02915-5>.
- [2] International Institute for Population Sciences, "National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–21: India," tech. rep., International Institute for Population Sciences, Deonar, Mumbai, India, 2021.
- [3] D. G. Dambhare, S. V. Wagh, and J. Y. Dudhe, "Age at menarche and menstrual cycle pattern among school adolescent girls in central india," *Global journal of health science*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 105, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.5539/gjhs.v4n1p105>.
- [4] P. K. Pathak, N. Tripathi, and S. Subramanian, "Secular trends in menarcheal age in india-evidence from the indian human development survey," *PLoS one*, vol. 9, no. 11, p. e111027, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0111027>.
- [5] M. Ahuja, "Age of menopause and determinants of menopause age: A PAN India survey by IMS," *Journal of mid-life health*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 126–131, 2016.
- [6] S. Pallikadavath, R. Ogollah, A. Singh, T. Dean, A. Dewey, and W. Stones, "Natural menopause among women below 50 years in India: A population-based study," *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, vol. 144, no. 3, pp. 366–377, 2016.
- [7] C. A. Agbaku, A. S. Yahaya, F. Junhua, S. Chengqi, and W. Linda, "Jute plant-a bio-degradable material in making sanitary pad for sustainable development," *Int. J. Sci. Res. Manag.*, vol. 8, pp. 162–170, 2020.
- [8] M. Mihm, S. Gangooly, and S. Muttukrishna, "The normal menstrual cycle in women," *Animal reproduction science*, vol. 124, no. 3–4, pp. 229–236, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2010.08.030>.
- [9] S. Karjee, M. Rahaman, and P. C. Biswas, "Contextualizing the socio-economic and spatial patterns of using menstrual hygienic methods among young women (15–24 years) in india: a cross-sectional study using the nationally representative survey," *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, vol. 20, p. 101253, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cegh.2023.101253>.
- [10] P. Aparnavi, R. Ramanathan, J. Shanmugam, S. Narayanan, M. Kumar, V. Ramya, R. Rathinamoorthy, and S. Vignesh, "Suitability, acceptability, feasibility of modern menstrual methods: a qualitative study in coimbatore district, tamil nadu, india," *Frontiers in Global Women's Health*, vol. 5, p. 1497686, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2024.1497686>.
- [11] G. Bhor and S. Ponskhe, "A decentralized and sustainable solution to the problems of dumping menstrual waste into landfills and related health hazards in india," *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 334–334, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.14207/ejsd.2018.v7n3p334>.
- [12] R. Ajwani-Ramchandani, "Disposable Sanitary Napkins: A Case of Single Use Plastic?," January 20 2020.
- [13] T. Research, "India Feminine Hygienic Product Market — By Product Type, By Distribution Channel, By Region, Competition, Forecast & Opportunities, 2020–2030F," 2025.
- [14] M. Sivakami, A. M. van Eijk, H. Thakur, N. Kakade, C. Patil, S. Shinde, N. Surani, A. Bauman, G. Zulaika, Y. Kabir, *et al.*, "Effect of menstruation on girls and their schooling, and facilitators of menstrual hygiene management in schools: surveys in government schools in three states in india. 2015," *Journal of global health*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 010408, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.7189/jogh.09.010408>.
- [15] R. Kaur, K. Kaur, and R. Kaur, "Menstrual hygiene, management, and waste disposal: practices and challenges faced by girls/women of developing countries," *Journal of environmental and public health*, vol. 2018, no. 1, p. 1730964, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/1730964>.
- [16] J. Ajmeri and C. Ajmeri, "Developments in the use of nonwovens for disposable hygiene products," in *Advances in technical nonwovens*, pp. 473–496, Elsevier, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100575-0.00018-8>.
- [17] K. E. Woeller and A. E. Hochwalt, "Safety assessment of sanitary pads with a polymeric foam absorbent core," *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 419–424, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2015.07.028>.
- [18] J. Blignaut, H. G. Visser, E. Erasmus, and M. Schutte-Smith, "sanitary pads—composition, regulation, and ongoing research to address associated challenges," *Journal of Materials Science*, pp. 1–47, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-025-11151-7>.
- [19] J. H. Shin and Y. G. Ahn, "Analysis of polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins and dibenzo-furans in sanitary products of women," *Textile Research Journal*, vol. 77, no. 8, pp. 597–603, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040517507078786>.
- [20] S. Ishii, R. Katagiri, T. Kataoka, M. Wada, S. Imai, and K. Yamasaki, "Risk assessment study of dioxins in sanitary napkins produced in japan," *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 357–362, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2014.07.020>.
- [21] H. Y. Kim, J. D. Lee, J.-Y. Kim, J. Y. Lee, O.-N. Bae, Y.-K. Choi, E. Baek, S. Kang, C. Min, K. Seo, *et al.*, "Risk assessment of volatile organic compounds (voc) detected in sanitary pads," *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part A*, vol. 82, no. 11, pp. 678–695, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15287394.2019.1642607>.
- [22] A. Mirzaie, M. Brandão, and H. Zarrabi, "Toward eco-friendly menstrual products: a comparative life cycle assessment of sanitary pads made from bamboo pulp vs. a conventional one," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 32, no. 14, pp. 9050–9067, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-025-36269-8>.
- [23] International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF, "National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4), 2015–2016," 2017. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.
- [24] A. Upadhyay, "Menstrual hygiene day facts: Only 36 percent of the women in India use sanitary pads during periods," *NDTV-Dettol Banega Swasth Swachh India*, 2019.
- [25] A. Biju, "Period product disposal in india: the tipping point," *The Lancet Regional Health-Southeast Asia*, vol. 15, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lansea.2023.100214>.
- [26] M. Aujla, C. H. Logie, A. Hardon, and M. Narasimhan, "Environmental impact of menstrual hygiene products," *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, vol. 103, no. 3, p. 223, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.24.291421>.
- [27] K. Upson, J. A. Shearston, and M.-A. Kioumourtoglou, "Menstrual products as a source of environmental chemical exposure: a review from the epidemiologic perspective," *Current environmental health reports*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 38–52, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-022-00331-1>.
- [28] Down To Earth, "India's landfills add 113k tonnes of menstrual waste each year: Report," June 2021.
- [29] P. B. Baruah, P. Dutta, and I. Buccha, "Are bio-degradable sanitary pads a smooth transition for women? a case study of assam," *Local Environment*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 534–545, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2024.2447752>.
- [30] S. Sasidaran, P. Kachoria, A. Raj, S. Ramalingam, B. R. Stoner, K. L. Sellgren, and S. Grego, "Physical properties of menstrual hygiene waste as feedstock for onsite disposal technologies," *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 474–482, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2021.262>.
- [31] U. Anand, M. Vithanage, A. U. Rajapaksha, A. Dey, S. Varjani, and E. Bontempi, "Inapt management of menstrual hygiene waste (mhw): An urgent global environmental and public health challenge in developed and developing countries," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 7, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09859>.
- [32] G. H. Brundtland, "Our common future world commission on environment and development," 1987.
- [33] "Rio declaration on environment and development, author=Declaration, Rio," 1992.
- [34] B. Purvis, Y. Mao, and D. Robinson, "Three pillars of sustainability: in search of conceptual origins," *Sustainability science*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 681–695, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0627-5>.

- [35] M. E. Harrison and N. Tyson, "Menstruation: Environmental impact and need for global health equity," 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.14311>.
- [36] B. Kumar, J. Singh, S. Mittal, and H. Singh, "The indian perspective on the harmful substances found in sanitary napkins and their effects on the environment and human health," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 31, no. 25, pp. 36217–36229, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-26739-2>.
- [37] C. J. Park, R. Barakat, A. Ulanov, Z. Li, P.-C. Lin, K. Chiu, S. Zhou, P. Perez, J. Lee, J. Flaws, *et al.*, "Sanitary pads and diapers contain higher phthalate contents than those in common commercial plastic products," *Reproductive Toxicology*, vol. 84, pp. 114–121, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2019.01.005>.
- [38] J. Ma, M. Chai, J. Li, S. Wang, and Z. Tang, "Occurrence of heavy metals in sanitary napkins from seven countries: implication for risk management of female hygiene products," *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, vol. 34, p. 103606, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2024.103606>.
- [39] Z. Tang, M. Chai, J. Cheng, Y. Wang, and Q. Huang, "Occurrence and distribution of phthalates in sanitary napkins from six countries: implications for women's health," *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 53, no. 23, pp. 13919–13928, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b03838>.
- [40] C.-J. Gao, F. Wang, H.-M. Shen, K. Kannan, and Y. Guo, "Feminine hygiene products—a neglected source of phthalate exposure in women," *Environmental Science & Technology*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 930–937, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b03927>.
- [41] D. Gosden, M. Studley, and J. Rossiter, "Material extrusion of sodium polyacrylate superabsorbent polymer," *Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 78, p. 103886, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2023.103886>.
- [42] M. F. Elledge, A. Muralidharan, A. Parker, K. T. Ravndal, M. Sidiqui, A. P. Toolaram, and K. P. Woodward, "Menstrual hygiene management and waste disposal in low and middle income countries—a review of the literature," *International journal of environmental research and public health*, vol. 15, no. 11, p. 2562, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15112562>.
- [43] S. Ray, S. Dey, A. K. Digo, K. K. Yadav, and A. P. Das, "Sanitary waste and microplastic pollution in the euro-mediterranean region: challenges and solutions," *Euro-Mediterranean Journal for Environmental Integration*, pp. 1–23, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41207-025-00879-y>.
- [44] M. Panjwani, Y. Rapolu, M. Chaudhary, M. Gulati, K. Razdan, A. Dhawan, and V. Sinha, "Biodegradable sanitary napkins—a sustainable approach towards menstrual and environmental hygiene," *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, vol. 14, no. 20, pp. 24911–24926, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-023-04688-7>.
- [45] N. P. Germolus, S.-N. Kim, J. Kim, and C. G. Park, "Safety assessment of commercial sanitary pads: Cytotoxicity, volatile organic compounds, and microplastics release," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, p. 139702, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.139702>.
- [46] M. S. A. Hameed, S. P. Sreedharan, P. Sivapragasam, S. Chakraborty, C. Devarajulu, and K. Sivagami, "Resource recovery from soiled sanitary napkin waste—a state-of-the-art review," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 31, no. 21, pp. 30336–30352, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-33218-9>.
- [47] J. Hand, C. Hwang, W. Vogel, C. Lopez, and S. Hwang, "An exploration of market organic sanitary products for improving menstrual health and environmental impact," *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 63–77, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2023.020>.
- [48] H. O. Critchley, E. Babayev, S. E. Bulun, S. Clark, I. Garcia-Grau, P. K. Gregersen, A. Kilcoyne, J.-Y. J. Kim, M. Lavender, E. E. Marsh, *et al.*, "Menstruation: science and society," *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology*, vol. 223, no. 5, pp. 624–664, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2020.06.004>.
- [49] D. Thampan, M. K. Jena, R. Hussain, M. Valliammai, M. S. A. Hameed, S. P. Sreedharan, and K. Sivagami, "Challenges and opportunities for implementing resource recovery from sanitary waste streams: insights from india," *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, pp. 1–21, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-025-02271-y>.
- [50] S. Fourcassier, M. Douziech, P. Pérez-López, and L. Schiebinger, "Menstrual products: A comparable life cycle assessment," *Cleaner Environmental Systems*, vol. 7, p. 100096, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2022.100096>.
- [51] A. Hait and S. E. Powers, "The value of reusable feminine hygiene products evaluated by comparative environmental life cycle assessment," *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, vol. 150, p. 104422, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104422>.
- [52] R. Boroah, H. Chanakya, and S. Dasappa, "Investigations into the performance of single chamber sanitary napkin incinerators with emphasis on co and co2 emissions," *Waste Management*, vol. 102, pp. 667–676, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.11.032>.
- [53] K. Babbar, J. Martin, J. Ruiz, A. A. Parray, and M. Sommer, "Menstrual health is a public health and human rights issue," *The Lancet Public Health*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. e10–e11, 2022.
- [54] S. Sood, S. Stevens, M. Okumura, M. Hauer, and A. Ramaiya, "A systematic review of menstrual health and hygiene management (mhmm) as a human right for adolescents girls," *International Journal of Sexual Health*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 483–502, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19317611.2022.2050874>.
- [55] B. Torondel, S. Sinha, J. R. Mohanty, T. Swain, P. Sahoo, B. Panda, A. Nayak, M. Bara, B. Bilung, O. Cumming, *et al.*, "Association between unhygienic menstrual management practices and prevalence of lower reproductive tract infections: a hospital-based cross-sectional study in odisha, india," *BMC infectious diseases*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. 473, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-018-3384-2>.
- [56] J. Marroquin, M.-A. Kiomourtzoglou, A. Scranton, and A. Z. Pollack, "Chemicals in menstrual products: a systematic review," *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, vol. 131, no. 5, pp. 655–664, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.17668>.
- [57] E. L. Eason and P. Feldman, "Contact dermatitis associated with the use of Always sanitary napkins," *CMAJ: Canadian Medical Association Journal*, vol. 154, no. 8, p. 1173, 1996.
- [58] W. G. Larsen, "Sanitary napkin dermatitis due to the perfume," *Archives of Dermatology*, vol. 115, no. 3, pp. 363–363, 1979.
- [59] B. Desmedt, Q. Marcelis, D. Zhilivoda, and E. Deconinck, "Sensitizing fragrances in absorbent hygiene products," *Contact Dermatitis*, vol. 82, no. 5, pp. 279–282, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cod.13472>.
- [60] C.-J. Gao and K. Kannan, "Phthalates, bisphenols, parabens, and triclocarban in feminine hygiene products from the united states and their implications for human exposure," *Environment international*, vol. 136, p. 105465, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105465>.
- [61] M. Rademaker, "Allergic contact dermatitis to a sanitary pad," *Australasian journal of dermatology*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 234–235, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-0960.2004.00105.x>.
- [62] M. Chakraborty and A. Singh, "Assessing the link between hygienic material use during menstruation and self-reported reproductive tract infections among women in India: a propensity score matching approach," *PeerJ*, vol. 11, p. e16430, 2023.
- [63] P. Das, K. K. Baker, A. Dutta, T. Swain, S. Sahoo, B. S. Das, B. Panda, A. Nayak, M. Bara, B. Bilung, *et al.*, "Menstrual hygiene practices, wash access and the risk of urogenital infection in women from odisha, india," *PloS one*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. e0130777, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0130777>.
- [64] J. Woo, S. Kim, H. Kim, K. S. Jeong, E. Kim, and E. Ha, "Systematic review on sanitary pads and female health," *The Ewha Medical Journal*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 25–38, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.12771/emj.2019.42.3.25>.
- [65] R. R. Tiwari, "Occupational health hazards in sewage and sanitary workers," *Indian journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 112–115, 2008.
- [66] G. Degavi, S. Debbarma, S. G. Adola, B. L. Safayi, U. Gameda, and T. Utura, "Occupational hazards and its relation with health-seeking and practicing behaviors among sanitary workers in southern, ethiopia," *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, vol. 15, p. 100339, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijans.2021.100339>.
- [67] The George Institute for Global Health, "Bloody Inconvenience: Menstrual Health in Waste Worker Communities," May 28 2022.
- [68] A. Tiwari, "Meet the Unsung Heroes of Waste Management—Rag-Picker Women," *Your Story*, 2018.
- [69] S. Kumari and U. Kiran, "Prevalence of health problems of rag pickers due to various hazards at lucknow city," *Human Factors in Healthcare*, vol. 2, p. 100023, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hfh.2022.100023>.
- [70] S. Badal, K. Holland, M. Foster, and A. B. Le, "The occupational safety and health risks of informal waste workers in nepal: A mapping review," *Safety and Health at Work*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2025.07.003>.
- [71] M. R. Ray, G. Mukherjee, S. Roychowdhury, and T. Lahiri, "Respiratory and general health impairments of ragpickers in india: a study in delhi," *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, vol. 77, no. 8, pp. 595–598, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00420-004-0564-8>.
- [72] W. Vogel, C. D. Hwang, and S. Hwang, "Gender and sanitation: women's experiences in rural regions and urban slums in india," *Societies*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 18, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc12010018>.
- [73] S. Parthasarathy, V. Jayaraman, S. Jeganathan, and A. R. Lakshminarayanan, "Menstrual hygiene and waste management: The survey results," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 65, pp. 3409–3416, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.05.531>.
- [74] R. Ashley, D. Blackwood, N. Souter, S. Hendry, J. Moir, J. Dunkerley, J. Davies, D. Butler, A. Cook, J. Conlin, *et al.*, "Sustainable disposal of domestic sanitary waste," *Journal of En-*

- Environmental Engineering*, vol. 131, no. 2, pp. 206–215, 2005. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9372\(2005\)131:2\(206\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9372(2005)131:2(206)).
- [75] N. Pandey and D. Kamle, “Building start-up ecosystem through social enterprise business model: A study reference to women empowerment by social enterprises,” in *INDAM: Indian Academy of Management at SBM-NMIMS Mumbai*, pp. 579–591, Springer, 2023. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-0197-5_36.
- [76] N. Pathak and J. Pradhan, “Menstrual management and low-cost sanitary napkins,” *Economic & Political Weekly*, vol. 51, no. 12, p. 27, 2016.
- [77] Times of India, “Sanitary disposal of pads in rural areas,” 2014.
- [78] P. Javadekar, “Sanitary pad disposal bags mandatory from January 2021,” 2020.
- [79] S. P. Deore, S. Kumar, S. M. Mahajani, and C. De Blasio, “Co-gasification of sanitary napkin with sawdust biomass in downdraft gasifier for thermal applications: An experimental approach,” *Energy*, vol. 276, p. 127562, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127562>.
- [80] A. Paul, P. Singh, and R. Panua, “Optimizing hydrogen-rich syngas production from sanitary waste via CO₂ gasification and pyrolysis,” *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, vol. 15, no. 10, pp. 15695–15711, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-024-06363-x>.
- [81] S. Deeb, “A right to menstrual health in a transition to a circular economy,” *Alternative Law Journal*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 40–45, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1037969X241309359>.
- [82] C. L. Luchese, J. B. Engel, and I. C. Tessaro, “Disposable, reusable and biodegradable hygiene products,” in *Antimicrobial Textiles from Natural Resources*, pp. 421–454, Elsevier, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-821485-5.00003-2>.
- [83] R. Agarwal, “A first-of-a-kind campaign in Pune creates awareness about sanitary waste segregation,” 2017.
- [84] The Indian Express, “Red-Dot campaign launched across Pune,” 2017.
- [85] M. I. Foundation, “PadCare Labs is Turning Used Sanitary Pads into Recycled Products,” 2025.
- [86] A. Bhattacharya, “Matka incinerators are revolutionising menstrual waste management in Uttar Pradesh,” 2025.
- [87] S. Garikipati, “Asymmetric information in menstrual health and implications for sustainability: Insights from india,” in *Sustainable Consumption and Production, Volume I: Challenges and Development*, pp. 391–412, Springer, 2021. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56371-4_19.
- [88] C. Kambala, A. Chinangwa, E. Chipeta, B. Torondel, and T. Morse, “Acceptability of menstrual products interventions for menstrual hygiene management among women and girls in malawi,” *Reproductive health*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 185, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-020-01045-z>.
- [89] S. Pednekar, S. Some, K. Rivankar, and R. Thakore, “Enabling factors for sustainable menstrual hygiene management practices: a rapid review,” *Discover Sustainability*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 28, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-022-00097-4>.
- [90] V. K. Kolil and K. Achuthan, “Development and validation of a survey instrument for reusable sanitary products toward sustainable menstrual hygiene,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 22062, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-72122-7>.
- [91] A. M. Van Eijk, N. Jayasinghe, G. Zulaika, L. Mason, M. Sivakami, H. W. Unger, and P. A. Phillips-Howard, “Exploring menstrual products: A systematic review and meta-analysis of reusable menstrual pads for public health internationally,” *PloS one*, vol. 16, no. 9, p. e0257610, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257610>.
- [92] S. D. Gölbaşı Koç, E. Yücel, S. Sungur, S. Metintaş, and M. F. Önsüz, “Use of menstrual cup and awareness of environmental effects of menstrual hygiene products,” *Local Environment*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 784–792, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2023.2179608>.
- [93] A. Peter and K. Abhitha, “Menstrual cup: A replacement to sanitary pads for a plastic free periods,” *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 47, pp. 5199–5202, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.05.527>.
- [94] K. Patel, S. Dwivedy, N. Panda, S. Swain, S. Pati, and S. K. Palo, “Is menstrual cup a sustainable and safe alternative in menstrual hygiene management? a qualitative exploratory study based on user’s experience in india,” *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, vol. 20, p. 101212, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cegh.2022.101212>.
- [95] S. Sadaf, F. Ahmad, A. Rasheed, Y. Nawab, S. Ahmad, F. Azam, and B. Mushtaq, “Sustainable sanitary pads: A comprehensive review of natural fibers and bio-based superabsorbent polymers for eco-friendly menstrual hygiene,” *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, p. 147524, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.147524>.
- [96] K. Mounika, K. Ilango, A. Baranitharan, S. Dhivyatharshini, K. Gowtham, V. Swetha, and S. Vijaykumar, “Biodegradable sanitary napkins an innovative approach towards menstrual hygiene using bamboo fiber and lemon grass,” *Int J Pharmaceut Sci*, vol. 1, no. 10, pp. 1–1, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10078084>.
- [97] J. Foster and P. Montgomery, “A study of environmentally friendly menstrual absorbents in the context of social change for adolescent girls in low-and middle-income countries,” *International journal of environmental research and public health*, vol. 18, no. 18, p. 9766, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18189766>.
- [98] S. Pawar, R. Farshi, A. G. Karegowda, P. Bhat, and P. MS, “Affordable, biodegradable, and environmentally friendly sanitary napkins for rural women, with a focus on degradation study,” *Results in Engineering*, vol. 24, p. 102988, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102988>.
- [99] I. Ghosh, D. Rakholia, K. Shah, D. Bhatt, and M. Das, “Environmental perspective on menstrual hygiene management along with the movement towards biodegradability: a mini-review,” *J Biomed Res Environ Sci*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 122–6, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.37871/JELS1129>.
- [100] R. Chakrabarty, “These two IIT Delhi boys created a reusable, biodegradable sanitary napkin made of banana fibre!,” 2019.
- [101] K. Achuthan, S. Muthupalani, V. K. Kolil, A. Bist, K. Sreesuthan, and A. Sreedevi, “A novel banana fiber pad for menstrual hygiene in india: a feasibility and acceptability study,” *BMC Women’s Health*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 129, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-021-01265-w>.
- [102] H. Kaur, “Examining the challenge of increasing consumer menstrual waste and exploring cloth pads as a viable alternative in the context of rural India,” 2020.
- [103] S. Anbalagan and M. Mani, “Design and characterization of eco-friendly feminine hygiene sanitary napkins from pineapple leaf fiber (palf) for a sustainable environment,” *Industrial Crops and Products*, vol. 219, p. 119031, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2024.119031>.
- [104] D. Rastogi, A. Jain, and B. Chanana, “Development of sanitary napkins using corn husk fibres in absorbent layer—an exploratory study,” *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, vol. 51, no. 2_suppl, pp. 2267S–2282S, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15280837211051103>.
- [105] T. Crofts and J. Fisher, “Menstrual hygiene in ugandan schools: an investigation of low-cost sanitary pads,” *Journal of water, sanitation and hygiene for development*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 50–58, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2012.067>.
- [106] L. Ganguly, L. Satpati, and S. Nath, “Papyrus to pad: an evolution of menstrual products,” *Asian Pacific Journal of Health Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 72–6, 2022.
- [107] M. K. Musaazi, A. R. Mechtenberg, J. Nakibuule, R. Sensenig, E. Miyingo, J. V. Makanda, A. Hakimian, and M. J. Eckelman, “Quantification of social equity in life cycle assessment for increased sustainable production of sanitary products in uganda,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 96, pp. 569–579, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.10.026>.
- [108] S. Chatterjee and V. Mishra, “Green chemistry—remedy to societal hygiene: a graphical review,” *Current Research in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, vol. 3, p. 100025, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crgsc.2020.100025>.
- [109] G. Sathishkumar, M. Aarthi, R. Senthilkumar, P. Nithiya, R. Selvakumar, and A. Bhattacharyya, “Biodegradable cellulosic sanitary napkins from waste cotton and natural extract based anti-bacterial nanocolorants,” *Journal of the Indian Institute of Science*, vol. 99, no. 3, pp. 519–528, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41745-019-00123-x>.
- [110] A. Rana, A. Mandal, B. Mitra, R. Jacobson, R. Rowell, and A. Banerjee, “Short jute fiber-reinforced polypropylene composites: Effect of compatibilizer,” *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 329–338, 1998.
- [111] N. Gibeop, D. Lee, C. V. Prasad, F. Toru, B. S. Kim, and J. I. Song, “Effect of plasma treatment on mechanical properties of jute fiber/poly (lactic acid) biodegradable composites,” *Advanced Composite Materials*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 389–399, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243046.2013.843814>.
- [112] V. BhanuRekha, C. Prakash, and K. Gowri, “Characterization of pulp extracted from agro-waste fibers using steam explosion technique,” *Journal of Natural Fibers*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 3529–3544, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15444078.2021.1961342>.
- [113] M. Sathianarayanan and S. Nitturkar, “Development of sustainable hygiene products from sugarcane bagasse,” *BTRA Scan*, vol. 54, no. 2, 2025.
- [114] H. Liu, Y. Zhang, and J. Yao, “Preparation and properties of an eco-friendly superabsorbent based on flax yarn waste for sanitary napkin applications,” *Fibers and Polymers*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 145–152, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12221-014-0145-8>.
- [115] B. Chanana, “Development of low cost Sanitary Napkins: Breaking MHM taboos of women in India,” *Int. J. Appl. Home Sci*, vol. 3, pp. 362–371, 2016.
- [116] A. Shahzad, “Hemp fiber and its composites—a review,” *Journal of composite materials*, vol. 46, no. 8, pp. 973–986, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998311413623>.
- [117] S. Sareen, “Sustainable menstrual alternatives: the journey so far,” *Int J Home Sci*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 216–219, 2021.

- [118] L. C. Initiative *et al.*, “Menstrual products and sustainable alternatives report 2021-Life Cycle Initiative,” 2021.
- [119] T. I. Express, “Just 0.06 kg non-biodegradable waste generated in lifetime by woman using menstrual cups: Report,” 2023.
- [120] S. D. Tiku, “Design and development of feminine reusable pad without pad holder,” *International Journal of Clothing Science and Technology*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 271–283, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCST-09-2018-0116>.
- [121] I. CSR, “How Sanitree is marshalling an eco-friendly revolution in menstrual hygiene,” 2021.
- [122] G. Wang and F. Chen, “Development of bamboo fiber-based composites,” in *Advanced high strength natural fibre composites in construction*, pp. 235–255, Elsevier, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100411-1.00010-8>.
- [123] K. O’BRIEN, R. Olive, Y.-C. Hsu, L. Morris, R. Bell, and N. Kendall, “Life cycle assessment: Reusable and disposable nappies in Australia,” *Environmental Engineering, School of Engineering, The University of Queensland, Brisbane*, 2009.
- [124] E. Vozzola, M. Overcash, and E. Griffing, “Environmental considerations in the selection of isolation gowns: a life cycle assessment of reusable and disposable alternatives,” *American journal of infection control*, vol. 46, no. 8, pp. 881–886, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2018.02.002>.
- [125] J. Choudhary and D. M. Bhattacharjee, “A study on consumption pattern of sanitary napkin and environment degradation,” *Int J Creative Res Thoughts (IJCRT)*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 11–6, 2018.
- [126] R. N. Sinha and B. Paul, “Menstrual hygiene management in India: The concerns,” 2018.
- [127] UNICEF India, “Clean India - Clean Schools: WASH contributes to healthier children in school and learning.”
- [128] A. Biswas and S. Tewari, “Sanitary waste management in India: Challenges and Agenda,” *Centre for Science and Environment, New Delhi*, 2022.
- [129] B. B. Nagar, “A comparative review of environmental impact of menstrual waste management in indian and global scenarios with a focus on single-use conventional sanitary products,” *Circular Economy and Sustainable Development: A Necessary Nexus for a Sustainable Future*, pp. 517–537, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66007-8_28.
- [130] R. Garg, S. Goyal, and S. Gupta, “India moves towards menstrual hygiene: subsidized sanitary napkins for rural adolescent girls—issues and challenges,” *Maternal and child health journal*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 767–774, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-011-0798-5>.
- [131] Press Information Bureau, Government of India, “Janaushadhi Suvidha Sanitary Napkin will now be available at One Rupee per pad,” 2020.
- [132] A. Bhagwat and P. Jijina, “A psychosocial lens on an indigenous initiative to address menstrual health and hygiene in indian villages,” *Social Work in Public Health*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 73–89, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19371918.2020.1738972>.
- [133] U. Ram, M. R. Pradhan, S. Patel, and F. Ram, “Factors associated with disposable menstrual absorbent use among young women in india,” *International Perspectives on Sexual and Reproductive Health*, vol. 46, pp. 223–234, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1363/46e0320>.
- [134] M. Chakrabarty, A. Singh, S. Let, and S. Singh, “Decomposing the rural–urban gap in hygienic material use during menstruation among adolescent women in india,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 22427, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-49682-1>.
- [135] D. Srivastava, A. Kumari, and S. P. Lal, “Factors influencing adoption of climate-friendly oxo-biodegradable jan ausadhi suvidha sanitary napkins among women in india,” *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 1754–1760, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.9734/IJECC/2022/v12i121622>.
- [136] United Nations Population Fund, “Supporting the Local Production of Low-Cost Hygiene Products in India,” August 2013.
- [137] Z. Zhongming, L. Linong, Y. Xiaona, Z. Wangqiang, and L. Wei, “A holistic approach to better menstrual health and hygiene: entrepreneurs in action,” *World Bank*, 2021.
- [138] We Are Water Foundation, “Creating Women Entrepreneurship Opportunities through Personal Hygiene and Sanitation Programme in Haiderpur, Haryana, India,” 2024.
- [139] U. Mahesh, “‘‘She care’’ Pads Turn Women into Entrepreneurs,” Oct 2023.
- [140] S. Dutta, R. Alekhya, B. Chakradhar, and T. S. S. Jyothsna, “Management and disposal of sanitary solid waste: an obscured menace in india,” *International Journal of Environment and Waste Management*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 217–233, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEW.2024.136946>.
- [141] M. D. Werner, M. C. Punzi, and A. Turkenburg, “Period power: Organizational stigma, multimodality, and social entrepreneurship in the menstrual products industry,” *Journal of Management Studies*, vol. 61, no. 5, pp. 2137–2180, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.12974>.
- [142] M. R. Behera, S. Parida, H. S. Pradhan, S. Priyabadini, R. K. Dehury, and B. Mishra, “Household sanitation and menstrual hygiene management among women: Evidence from household survey under Swachh Bharat (Clean India) Mission in rural Odisha, India,” *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1100–1108, 2022.
- [143] F. Jahan, M. Nuruzzaman, F. Sultana, M. T. Mahfuz, M. Rahman, F. Akhand, S. P. Luby, L. Unicomb, and P. J. Winch, “Piloting an acceptable and feasible menstrual hygiene products disposal system in urban and rural schools in bangladesh,” *BMC Public Health*, vol. 20, no. 1, p. 1366, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09413-x>.
- [144] G. Khanal, N. Shrestha, K. Adhikari, and U. Ghimire, “Menstruation hygiene management among secondary school students of chitwan, nepal: a cross-sectional study,” *BMC women’s health*, vol. 23, no. 1, p. 395, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-023-02494-x>.
- [145] A. Suleman, S. Krishna, D. Krishnakumar, K. Nemoto, M. L. T. Nguyen, and S. D. Mehta, “A pilot survey of students’ menstrual attitudes, experiences, and needs on an urban university campus,” *Women’s Health*, vol. 20, p. 17455057241254713, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17455057241254713>.
- [146] P. Acheampong, K. Akodwaa-Boadi, E. Appiah-Effah, and K. B. Nyarko, “WASH infrastructure and menstrual hygiene management in basic schools: a study in Kumasi, Ghana,” 2018.
- [147] A. Bhakta, A. Mansuri, J. Jaiswal, and M. Iyer, “The need of the hour: Providing water in shared toilet facilities for menstrual hygiene management in urban india,” *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 113–121, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2024.265>.
- [148] UNICEF, “Guidance on Menstrual Health and Hygiene,” 2019.
- [149] J. Hennegan and P. Montgomery, “Do menstrual hygiene management interventions improve education and psychosocial outcomes for women and girls in low and middle income countries? a systematic review,” *PloS one*, vol. 11, no. 2, p. e0146985, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0146985>.
- [150] E. Peberdy, A. Jones, and D. Green, “A study into public awareness of the environmental impact of menstrual products and product choice,” *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 2, p. 473, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11020473>.
- [151] V. Miller and I. T. Winkler, “Transnational engagements: Menstrual health and hygiene—emergence and future directions,” *The Palgrave Handbook of Critical Menstruation Studies*, pp. 653–666, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-0614-7_48.
- [152] P. Montgomery, J. Hennegan, C. Dolan, M. Wu, L. Steinfield, and L. Scott, “Menstruation and the cycle of poverty: a cluster quasi-randomised control trial of sanitary pad and puberty education provision in uganda,” *PloS one*, vol. 11, no. 12, p. e0166122, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0166122>.
- [153] L. Rossouw and H. Ross, “Understanding period poverty: socio-economic inequalities in menstrual hygiene management in eight low-and middle-income countries,” *International journal of environmental research and public health*, vol. 18, no. 5, p. 2571, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18052571>.
- [154] D. N. Alugnoa, T. Cousins, and M. Sato, “Period poverty and menstrual belonging: a matter of climate justice,” *The Lancet Planetary Health*, vol. 6, no. 7, pp. e551–e552, 2022.
- [155] S. Mann and S. K. Byrne, “Period poverty from a public health and legislative perspective,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 20, no. 23, p. 7118, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20237118>.
- [156] A. Singh, M. Chakrabarty, S. Singh, R. Chandra, S. Chowdhury, and A. Singh, “Menstrual hygiene practices among adolescent women in rural india: a cross-sectional study,” *BMC Public Health*, vol. 22, no. 1, p. 2126, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-14622-7>.
- [157] A. Bhartiya, “Menstruation, religion and society,” *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, vol. 3, no. 6, p. 523, 2013.
- [158] I. Johnston-Robledo and J. C. Chrisler, “The menstrual mark: Menstruation as social stigma,” *The Palgrave handbook of critical menstruation studies*, pp. 181–199, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-0614-7_17.
- [159] R. Karki and C. Espinosa, “Breaking Taboos: Menstruation, Female Subordination and Reproductive Health, the Case of India,” *Insights Anthropology*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 111–20, 2018.
- [160] T. Mahon and M. Fernandes, “Menstrual hygiene in south asia: a neglected issue for wash (water, sanitation and hygiene) programmes,” *Gender & Development*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 99–113, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552071003600083>.
- [161] R. M. Kowalski and T. Chapple, “The social stigma of menstruation: Fact or fiction?,” *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 74–80, 2000. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-6402.2000.tb01023.x>.
- [162] M. L. Stubbs and D. Costos, “Negative attitudes toward menstruation: Implications for disconnection within girls and between women,” in *From Menarche to Menopause*, pp. 37–54, Routledge, 2014. https://doi.org/10.1300/J015v27n03_04.
- [163] M. Sommer, S. Chandraratna, S. Cavill, T. Mahon, and P. Phillips-Howard, “Managing menstruation in the workplace: an over-

- looked issue in low-and middle-income countries,” *International journal for equity in health*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 86, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-016-0379-8>.
- [164] J. E. Glayzer, E. J. Glayzer, C. T. Jennings, J. M. Schlaeger, A. Lee, and B. C. Bray, “Enhancing menstrual equity: An observational study assessing the impact of free little period product pantries,” *Women’s Health*, vol. 20, p. 17455057241306666, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17455057241306666>.
- [165] A. M. Van Eijk, M. Sivakami, M. B. Thakkar, A. Bauman, K. F. Laserson, S. Coates, and P. A. Phillips-Howard, “Menstrual hygiene management among adolescent girls in india: a systematic review and meta-analysis,” *BMJ open*, vol. 6, no. 3, p. e010290, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-010290>.
- [166] P. Ahuja and N. Singh, “Comprehending women beliefs towards sustainable menstrual products—a fundamental step in healthcare,” *International Journal of Human Rights in Healthcare*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 629–644, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHRH-08-2023-0068>.
- [167] J. Pal, S. Ahmad, and A. Siva, “Impact of health education regarding menstrual hygiene on genitourinary tract morbidities: an intervention study among adolescent girl students in an urban slum,” *Int J Res Med Sci*, vol. 5, no. 11, pp. 4937–41, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20174948>.
- [168] K. B. Rai, “The Impact of Menstrual Hygiene Education on School Attendance Among Adolescent Girls in Rural Nepal: A Case Study of Gorkha District,” *Journal of Research in Social Science and Humanities*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 1–5, 2024.
- [169] S. Ghosh, “Advancing Women’s Health and Dignity: A Comprehensive Analysis of Menstrual Health Management and Rights in India,” in *Law and Emerging Issues*, pp. 141–150, Routledge, 2024.
- [170] S. Biswas, A. Alam, N. Islam, R. Roy, and L. Satpati, “Understanding period product use among young women in rural and urban india from a geospatial perspective,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 20114, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-70383-w>.